

MOUNTAINS UNCOVERED

Intercomparable Maps and Statistics for 100 Selected Global Mountain Ranges

High Plateaux of Katanga

#8

High Plateaux of Katanga

The *Mountains Uncovered* series has been developed by GEO Mountains to provide a set of easily understandable and inter-comparable maps, tables, and figures spanning a range of thematic areas for 100 selected global mountain ranges. This is the report for the **High Plateaux of Katanga** mountain range. The [index page](#) shows an overview of all mountain ranges in the series.

Location of the High Plateaux of Katanga mountain range [1][2].

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1. General Information

1.1. Administrative

The mountain range has spatial overlap with **two** different countries, as shown in Figure 1.1. The overview is based on the GADM dataset [3] of administrative divisions at Level 0.

Figure 1.1. Administrative Overview

Map showing the administrative divisions overlapping with the mountain range.

Data: GADM [3] Background: GMBA [2], GADM [3], Natural Earth [3], Geonames [4], World Bank [22].

1.2. Demographics

Data on the mountain range's human population are sourced from the European Commission's GHS-POP dataset [5]. According to this source, it is estimated that **98,681** people lived in the area in 2020. This is expected to **increase to 223,737** by 2030. There are **no large settlements** listed in the populated places database.

In 2020, the human population in this mountain range was estimated to be 98,681.

Figure 1.2. Population estimates in the mountain range from 1975-2030. The data after 2020 are projections.

The maps show the population density in the mountain range (Figure 1.3), and estimated travel time to the nearest population centre with more than 50,000 inhabitants (Figure 1.4). Estimated travel time can be useful for evaluating accessibility to services and markets.

Figure 1.3. Population Density

Figure 1.4. Travel Time

1.3. Development and Economic Indicators

The Human Development Index (HDI) is determined by a combination of indicators such as life expectancy, literacy rate, access to electricity, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and others. In 2015, the average HDI in this mountain range was estimated to be **0.44**. This is considered to be a **low level of development**.

The total GDP within this mountain range in 2015 was estimated to be **\$190 million**, an **increase of \$112 million since 2000**. Table 1.2. shows an overview of the HDI and GDP indicators over time.

Table 1.2. GDP and HDI Indicators over Time

	1990	2000	2015
Gross Domestic Product	\$90 M	\$78 M	\$190 M
Human Development Index	0.36	0.33	0.44

Source: Kummu et al. [7]

1.4. Protected Areas

Figure 1.3 shows the spatial coverage of protected areas in the mountain range according to the World Database of Protected Areas (WDPA) [8]. A total of **52%** of the mountain range is covered by a protected area. The establishment of protected areas represents a key measure to protect and conserve valuable mountain biodiversity and ecosystems. These areas vary broadly in their aims, regulations, and effectiveness, however.

Figure 1.3. Protected Areas

A total of 52% of the mountain range is classified as protected in the World Database of Protected Areas.

The largest protected areas are:

1. Bassin de la Lufira	43,684 km ²
Ramsar Site, Wetland of International Importance	
2. Upemba	13,526 km ²
National Park	
3. Kundelungu	8,092 km ²
National Park	
4. Lubudi-Sampwe	3,439 km ²
Hunting Area	

2. Land cover

2.1. Land Cover

According to the ESA WorldCover dataset [9], the most dominant land cover types in 2021 were **tree cover (84.7%)**.

Figure 2.1. Land Cover

Land cover percentages from 2021 for the largest land cover classes in the mountain range.

The European Commission's Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) [10] classifies **0.1%** of the mountain range's area as urban centre, **0.1%** as urban cluster, and **99.9%** as rural.

3. Topography

The land surface elevation ranges from a **minimum of 572 m** to a **maximum of 1,826 m**. The **mean elevation is 1,175 m**. **50%** of the area lies is between **978 m and 1,376 m**, and **90%** of the area lies **between 764 m and 1,516 m**. Figure 3.1 shows a shaded relief elevation map based on the MERIT DEM [11] and a selection of peaks from the Geonames dataset [4]. The distribution of land surface elevation strongly affects local climatic and living conditions in mountains.

Figure 3.2. Distribution of elevation within in the mountain range [11].

Figure 3.3. Distribution of slope steepness within in the mountain range [21].

Figure 3.1. Elevation and Peaks

4. Climate

4.1. Temperature and Precipitation

Precipitation and temperature combine to control local weather and climate, with implications for water availability, vegetation growing conditions, snow and ice accumulation, and extreme events such as floods and droughts.

The mean annual temperature across the mountain range is shown in Figure 4.1. The **mean annual temperature for the entire mountain range is 21.8°C**, but it varies geographically from a **minimum of 17.5°C** to a **maximum of 26.5°C**. The temperature data are extracted from the CHELSA climatology dataset [13].

The mean annual precipitation shown in Figure 4.2. The **mean annual precipitation for the entire mountain range is 1,337 mm**, but it varies geographically from a **minimum of 1,006 mm** to a **maximum of 1,833 mm**. Precipitation data are bias-corrected for use in mountain environments, and are extracted from CHELSA data in the Precipitation Bias CORrection (PBCOR) dataset [12].

Figure 4.1. Mean Annual Temperature

Figure 4.2. Mean Annual Precipitation

The mean monthly temperature across the entire mountain range shown in Figure 4.3, and varies from a **maximum of 23.8°C in September** to a **minimum of 20.8°C in January**. Equivalent statistics for precipitation are shown in Figure 4.4, which vary from a **maximum of 243 mm in December** to a **minimum of 0 mm in July**.

Figure 4.3. Mean Monthly Temperature

Data: CHELSA [13].

Figure 4.4. Mean Monthly Precipitation

Data: CHELSA/PBCOR [12].

4.2. Climate Classifications

Figures 4.5 and Figure 4.6 show Köppen-Geiger climate classifications for the present day (1980-2016) and for projected future conditions (2071-2100), respectively. Future conditions are derived from an ensemble of 32 climate model projections under the RCP 8.5 "business-as-usual" scenario [14].

Figure 4.5. Current Climate Classifications

Köppen-Geiger climate classification for the present day (1980-2016).

Data: GloH2O [14]. Background: GMBA [2], GADM [3], Natural Earth [3], Geonames [4], World Bank [22].

Figure 4.6. Future Climate Classifications

Köppen-Geiger climate classification for ensemble mean projected future conditions (2071-2100) under the RCP 8.5 scenario.

Data: GloH2O [14]. Background: GMBA [2], GADM [3], Natural Earth [3], Geonames [4], World Bank [22].

Table 4.1. Changes in climate classifications between current (1980-2016) and future (2071-2100) conditions

Classification	Current	Future	Change
Aw Tropical, savannah	74.2%	100.0%	▲ 25.8%
Cwb Temperate, dry winter, warm summer	13.2%	0.0%	▼ 13.2%
Cwa Temperate, dry winter, hot summer	12.2%	0.0%	▼ 12.2%

Source: GloH2O [14].

5. Hydrology

According to the GRDC Major River Basins dataset, **two major basins** intersect the mountain range [15]. The **Congo has the most overlap with 100%** and drains into the **South Atlantic**.

Within the mountain range, there are a total of **one dams** listed in the Global Reservoirs and Dams (GRaND) database [16]. The main usage of this dams is **none (1)**. The total capacity of these dams is estimated to be **25 million m³**. Figure 5.1 shows major rivers, basins, and dams (red points) that intersect with this mountain range.

Figure 5.1. Major Rivers, Basins, and Dams.

Data: GRDC [15], GRaND [16]. Background: GMBA [2], GADM [3], Natural Earth [3], Geonames [4], World Bank [22].

Dams in this mountain range with the most capacity [16].

N'Seke 25 Mm³

6. Cryosphere

6.1. Glaciers and Permafrost

According to the Randolph Glacier Inventory dataset there are **no glaciers** in this mountain range [17].

6.2. Snow Cover

The average snow covered area in this mountain range does not exceed 1%, even in the coldest months. Maps and charts of snow covered area are therefore not shown.

7. Measurement Locations

The GEO Mountains Inventory of In Situ Observational Infrastructure (v2.0) lists a total of **zero measurement sites** in this mountain range [20]. Their locations are shown as red dots in Figure 7.1. In situ measurements are crucial for a range of scientific and practical application in mountains, yet the locations of measurement sites are often difficult to gain an appreciation of. Measurement sites include weather and climate stations, river gauging stations, networks of stations, experimental basins, and others.

Figure 7.1. Locations of Measurement Sites

According to the GEO Mountains Inventory of In Situ Observational Infrastructure, there are zero measurement sites in this mountain range

References

- Natural Earth Data. Via <https://www.naturalearthdata.com>.
- GMBA Mountain Inventory v2. Snethlage, M.A., Geschke, J., Spehn, E.M., Ranipeta, A., Yoccoz, N.G., Körner, Ch., Jetz, W., Fischer, M. & Urbach, D. A hierarchical inventory of the world's mountains for global comparative mountain science. *Nature Scientific Data*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01256-y> (2022). Dataset: Snethlage, M.A., Geschke, J., Spehn, E.M., Ranipeta, A., Yoccoz, N.G., Körner, Ch., Jetz, W., Fischer, M. & Urbach, D. GMBA Mountain Inventory v2. *GMBA-EarthEnv*. <https://doi.org/10.48601/earthenv-t9k2-1407> (2022).
- GADM Global Administrative Divisions. Via <https://www.gadm.org/>.
- Geonames geographical database. Via <https://www.geonames.org/>.
- GHS-POP layer of the Global Human Settlement Dataset. Dataset: Schiavina M., Freire S., MacManus K. (2022): GHS-POP R2022A - GHS population grid multitemporal (1975-2030). European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) PID: <http://data.europa.eu/89h/d6d86a90-4351-4508-99c1-cb074b022c4a>, doi:10.2905/D6D86A90-4351-4508-99C1-CB074B022C4A
- Global Accessibility Map. Via <https://forobs.jrc.ec.europa.eu/products/gam/>.
- Kummu, M., Taka, M. & Guillaume, J. Gridded global datasets for Gross Domestic Product and Human Development Index over 1990–2015. *Sci Data* 5, 180004 (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2018.4>
- UNEP-WCMC and IUCN (2022), Protected Planet: The World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA) Cambridge, UK: UNEP-WCMC and IUCN. Available at: www.protectedplanet.net.
- ESA WorldCover project 2023. Contains modified Copernicus Sentinel data, processed by ESA WorldCover consortium 2021. Via: <https://esa-worldcover.org/>.
- Global Human Settlement Dataset (SMOD Layers). Schiavina M., Melchiorri M., Pesaresi M. (2022): GHS-SMOD R2022A - GHS settlement layers, application of the Degree of Urbanisation methodology (stage I) to GHS-POP R2022A and GHS-BUILT-S R2022A, multitemporal (1975-2030) European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) PID: <http://data.europa.eu/89h/4606d58a-dc08-463c-86a9-d49ef461c47f>, doi:10.2905/4606D58A-DC08-463C-86A9-D49EF461C47F
- MERIT DEM. Yamazaki D., D. Ikeshima, R. Tawatari, T. Yamaguchi, F. O'Loughlin, J.C. Neal, C.C. Sampson, S. Kanae & P.D. Bates A high accuracy map of global terrain elevations *Geophysical Research Letters*, vol.44, pp.5844-5853, 2017 doi: 10.1002/2017GL072874. Available via http://hydro.iis.u-tokyo.ac.jp/~yamada/MERIT_DEM/.
- GloH2O PBCOR dataset: Beck, H. E., T. R. McVicar, M. Zambrano-Bigiarini, C. Alvarez-Garret, O. M. Baez-Villanueva, J. Sheffield, D. Karger, and E. F. Wood, 2020 Bias correction of global high-resolution precipitation climatologies using streamflow observations from 9372 catchments *Journal of Climate* 33, 1299–1315, doi:10.1175/JCLI-D-19-0332.1
- CHELSA V2.1 climatologies. Karger, D.N., Conrad, O., Böhrner, J., Kawohl, T., Kreft, H., Soria-Auza, R.W., Zimmermann, N.E., Linder, P., Kessler, M. (2017): Climatologies at high resolution for the Earth land surface areas. *Scientific Data*. 4 170122. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2017.122> Available via: <https://chelsa-climate.org/>
- Beck, H.E., N.E. Zimmermann, T.R. McVicar, N. Vergopolan, A. Berg, E.F. Wood. Present and future Köppen-Geiger climate classification maps at 1-km resolution *Scientific Data* 5:180214, doi:10.1038/sdata.2018.214 (2018)
- GRDC (2020): Major River Basins of the World / Global Runoff Data Centre, GRDC. 2nd, rev. ext. ed. Koblenz, Germany: Federal Institute of Hydrology (BfG). Available via <https://www.bafg.de/GRDC/>
- Lehner, B., C. Reidy Liermann, C. Revenga, C. Vörösmarty, B. Fekete, P. Crouzet, P. Döll, M. Endejan, K. Frenken, J. Magome, C. Nilsson, J.C. Robertson, R. Rodel, N. Sindorf, and D. Wisser. 2011. High-resolution mapping of the world's reservoirs and dams for sustainable river-flow management. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment* 9 (9): 494-502.
- Randolph Glacier Inventory 6.0. Via: <https://www.glims.org/RGI/>
- Permafrost Zonation Index. Gruber, S. 2012: Derivation and analysis of a high-resolution estimate of global permafrost zonation, *The Cryosphere*, 6, 221-233 Via <https://climatedataguide.ucar.edu/climate-data/global-permafrost-zonation-index-map>
- ESA-CCI Snow Cover Fraction data. Via: <https://snow-cci.enveo.at/>
- GEO Mountains (2022). Inventory of in situ mountain observational infrastructure, v2.0. DOI: 10.6084/m9.figshare.14899845.v2 Via: <https://www.geomountains.org/resources/resources-surveys/inventory-of-in-situ-observational-infrastructure>
- Amatulli, G., McInerney, D., Sethi, T. et al. Geomorpho90m, empirical evaluation and accuracy assessment of global high-resolution geomorphometric layers. *Sci Data* 7, 162 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0479-6>
- World Bank administrative boundaries and disputed borders (2023) via <https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/search/dataset/0038272>

Index

The index shows an overview of the 100 mountain ranges in version v1.0 of the *Mountains Uncovered* series.

Africa

1. Albertine Rift Mountains
2. Central Range (Madagascar)
3. Drakensberg
4. Eastern Arc Mountains
5. Eastern Rift mountains
6. Ethiopian Highlands
7. High Atlas Range
8. High Plateaux of Katanga
9. Horn of Africa Highlands
10. Middle Atlas
11. Northeastern Great Escarpment
12. Plateau of Mozambique
13. Rif
14. Southern Rift Mountains
15. Tell Atlas

Eurasia

16. Alborz Mountains
17. Altyn-Tagh
18. Armenian Highlands
19. Baetic System
20. Balkan Mountains
21. Balochistan Ranges
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23. Cantabrian Mountains
24. Carpathian Mountains
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Eurasia (continued)

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27. Central Range (Papua New Guinea)
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32. Hellenides
33. Hengduan Shan
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35. Hindu Kush
36. Honshu
37. Karakoram
38. Kunlun Mountains
39. Kuznetsk Alatau
40. Min Mountains
41. Mongolian Altai
42. Mongolian Highlands
43. Northern Altai
44. Northern Scandes
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46. Pontic Mountains
47. Pyrenees
48. Qiangtang
49. Qilian Mountains
50. Qionglai Shan

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53. Sistema Iberico
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57. Tangula Mountains
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59. Tian Shan
60. Transhimalaya
61. Ural Mountains
62. Western Sayan
63. Yunnan-Guizhou Plateau
64. Zagros Mountains

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67. British Columbia Interior
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70. Central Montana Rocky Mountains
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97. Dry Andes
98. Meseta Patagónica
99. Patagonian Andes
100. Sierras Pampeanas

About the Series

Aims

The *Mountains Uncovered* series (v1.0) aims to provide an easily understandable overview of the key characteristics of 100 selected mountain ranges around the world. Comparisons between mountain ranges can also readily be made. The series was developed by collating and visualising a variety of current global scale data products. We hope that the series will be a useful resource for researchers, policy-makers, environmental managers, educators, and others seeking to better understand the Earth's major mountain regions, and that over time it will inspire the generation of additional datasets, analyses, and products.

Citation and Sharing

The *Mountains Uncovered* series (v1.0) has been developed on the basis of exclusively open global spatial datasets. In turn, all visualisations, statistics, and code generated are shared under the [Creative Commons BY 4.0](#) license. You may use, distribute, and reproduce the product in any medium, provided appropriate acknowledgement is given. Please cite the series as:

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GEO Mountains assumes no responsibility and accepts no liability for the product's use, and remains neutral with respect to the locations of any borders and the place names shown in the third-party datasets employed.

Limitations

Users should note that data and information are limited in many mountain regions around the world. As a result, the figures, maps, and graphs presented in this series are associated with uncertainties, and these uncertainties must be taken into account when interpreting the information given.

To ensure that any comparisons made between individual mountain ranges are as fair as possible, global-scale datasets were used (without any additional modification). Consequently, the series does not necessarily represent a compendium of the "best" data available in any given mountain range or local area, but rather a common, generally intercomparable set. For applications at local and regional scales, alternative datasets to those shown may be more suitable.

Indeed, in parallel to the ongoing development of the global series, more local and regional "bottom-up" engagements and activities to improve the quality and availability of data should also be undertaken, since data on these scales also play a crucial role in supporting decision-making for the benefit of mountain people and ecosystems.

Get Involved

While many global mountain regions remain notoriously data-scarce, new datasets are being released regularly. If you are aware of any datasets you would like us to consider including in a potential future release, please provide the necessary details via [this form](#). Likewise, if you become aware of any errors, omissions, or other potential modifications that could be made in a future version, please let us know via the same form. By taking these actions, you will help us expand the scope and improve the impact of the *Mountains Uncovered* series. Feedback concerning the underlying datasets will be collated and shared with the relevant organisations or data providers.

Contact

For any general queries or comments, please contact: geomountains@mountainresearchinitiative.org

Many thanks for your interest, support, and contributions to global mountain data, policy, and education!

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About GEO Mountains

GEO Mountains is an Initiative of the Group on Earth Observations (GEO). It aims to bring together research institutions and mountain observation networks to enhance the discoverability, accessibility, and use of a wide range of relevant data and information pertaining to environmental and socio-economic systems – both in situ and remotely sensed – across global mountain regions. In doing so, we hope to help facilitate scientific advancements and support decision makers at local, national, and regional levels. The figure below illustrates the scope of the Initiative.

GEO Mountains is an open and inclusive network. We aspire to follow the principles of open data and open science wherever possible.

